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Nutritional Impact Of Intestinal Parasitic Infections Among Primary School Children In Gombe State

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ABSTRACT

Intestinal parasitic infections (IPIs) are a significant public health concern particularly in low and middle income countries, where they contribute to high morbidity and mortality rates among children among children. This study assessed the prevalence, species distribution and nutritional impact of IPIs among primary school children in Gombe State, A cross-sectional study was conducted among One Thousand Two Hundred children across six schools from six randomly selected Local Government Areas. Stool samples were examined for intestinal parasites using Kato Katz and Formol Ether Concentration (FEC) Technique and anthropometric indices were used to evaluate nutritional status. The indices were measured using the Anthroplus software; it was determined by the Z-score value. Biochemical parameters measured following the standard procedures include haemoglobin concentration, serum ferritin, creatinine and albumin levels. The prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections was 26.75%. The most common intestinal parasites were *Ascaris lumbricoides* (10.5%), *Entamoeba coli* (3.5%) and Hookworm (1.95%). Age- related prevalence showed the highest infection in children aged 5-9 years 127 (30.6%) and the least in those aged 10-12 years 144 (24.8%) ($p < 0.05$). Infections were slightly higher in females (27.2%) than in males (26.1%) ($p < 0.05$). Infection varied significantly by location, with Balanga having the highest prevalence (35.0%) and Kwami the lowest (19.0%). Nutritional assessments revealed that infected children had higher rates of stunting (moderate: 20.2%, severe: 3.1%) and underweight status (moderate: 28.3%, severe: 8.7%). However, wasting was higher in non-infected children (60.9%). ($p < 0.05$). Anemia was significantly more prevalent among infected children (14.3%) compared to non-infected (2.3%). There was a significant ferritin deficiency in infected compared to non infected children. However, creatinine and albumin level were normal among infected and non infected children. These findings underscore the interplay between intestinal parasitic infections, anaemia and malnutrition, highlighting the need for integrated school-based deworming programs, nutritional interventions, improved hygiene education, and enhanced water and sanitation infrastructure to reduce the burden of Intestinal Parasitic Infections among school children in Gombe State.

Keywords: Intestinal parasitic infections, water, sanitation

1. INTRODUCTION

The protozoan parasites (*Entamoeba histolytica* and *Giardia intestinalis/lambliia*) and soil-transmitted helminthes (*Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura*, and *Hookworm*) are the most prevalent intestinal parasites causing high morbidity and mortality in sub-Saharan Africa, affecting nearly all inhabitants at some point in their lives as stated by Baye *et al.*(2020). Parasitic infections affect the poorest and deprived communities of low and middle-income countries of the tropical and subtropical regions (Thomas *et al.*, 2015). The main reasons for the high prevalence of parasite infections in tropical and subtropical countries are increasing population density, poor sanitation conditions, poor public health practices, inadequate toilet facilities, contaminated food and water, malnutrition, low host resistance and environmental changes (Unasho *et al.*,2013).

Malnutrition is a common health problem of African school children due to intestinal parasitic infections and many other factors (Amare *et al.*, 2013). The capacity of parasites to alter the host nutritional balance means that host-parasite relations are always dynamic. Chronic infections, which are characteristic of human malaria and intestinal parasitic infections can lead to marked changes in host nutritional state, maintaining or increasing susceptibility to further infection. An aspect of this process which has received little attention in published reports is that changes in host nutrition induced by one species of parasite not only influence that species but influence all the other parasites to which the host is exposed. Poly parasitism, the state of infection with multiple infectious agents, is the normal conditioning endemic areas and, thus, the overall interactions between nutrition and parasitism in a given host individual are likely to be very complex (Robert *et al.*, 2001). Anemia is also one of the nutritional problems that are still huge. According to the WHO classification, anemia in women and children is still a public health problem in the severe category. Crompton, (2000) noted that among parasitic infections, malaria, trichuriasis and schistosomiasis are known to contribute to poor iron status and iron-deficiency anaemia. Further, these infections, singly or in combination, often occurred concurrently with hookworm, in the same individual person.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Description of the Study Area

A school based cross sectional study was carried out in Gombe State, North- Eastern Nigeria, which lies between latitude 10° 11' 36" N and 10° 19' 26" N and longitude 11° 7' 34" E and 11° 11' 26" E of the Greenwich Meridian. Gombe State has an area of 20,265km² and a population of around 2,365,000 people as of 2006. The average annual temperature is about 24°C and annual rainfall of between 850 mm and 1000 mm, relative humidity ranges from 15-80%. The area experiences two seasons, the wet season (April-October) and dry season (November-March) with a Sudan-Sahelian savanna vegetation. Temperature can reach up to 38°C during the day and humidity less than 20% (Grema *et al.*, 2014). Gombe State has 11 Local Government Areas. It is grouped into three geopolitical zones namely: South, North and Central zones. The study was carried out in all the zones with both urban and rural settlements.

Comprehensive lists of all the schools within the randomly selected Local Government areas were obtained from Gombe State Universal Primary Education Board. One School was systematically selected from six (6) Local Government area of the State. (Two Local Governments each from the three geopolitical zones) the Local Governments Areas selected are: Balanga, Shongom, Bajoga, Gombe, Kwami and Akko.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval with the reference number MOH/ADM/621/VOL.1/416 was obtained from the ethical committee Gombe State Ministry of Health before the commencement of the research.

Consent/Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Participants were assured of the confidentiality of data collected. Advocacy visits were made to the Executive Education Secretaries of the selected Local Governments Areas to solicit for their support. The head teachers of selected primary schools were visited with the ethical clearance Written consents and assents was collected respectively, from the student's parents/guardians and the participating children, after explaining the purpose and procedures. Those children who/whose guardians signed informed

consent and delivered stool and blood samples were included. Students who did not signed informed consent; those who did not properly collect their stool sample were excluded from the study.

Sampling and Processing

Fresh stool samples were collected from each study subject. The children were instructed properly and given clean, labeled, sterile, wide mouthed capped plastic containers along with applicator sticks. Brief instructions on how to collect stool so as to avoid contamination with water, soil and urine was given. From each student, about 4g of fresh stool was collected. At the time of collection, date of sampling, school name, age, code and sex were recorded for each subject in a recording format. Stool samples were preserved in 10% formalin to preserve the parasitic eggs and then carried in a confined carton box immediately to the Parasitological Laboratory of Federal Teaching Hospital Gombe on the same day of collection for parasitological examination.

2mls of blood was collected from each child from the median cubital vein at the elbow using syringe and tourniquet with the help of medical personnel. The blood samples were immediately transferred into an EDTA sample bottle. The blood samples were then transported to Haematology and Chemical Pathology Laboratory of Federal Teaching Hospital Gombe for processing.

Determination of Anthropometric Indices

Anthropometric measurements were taken by considering sex, age, height and weight of the students. A portable battery powered digital balance was used to measure weight and height of each student to the nearest 0.1 kg and 0.1 cm, respectively. The height and weight measurements were taken in a minimum cloth and without shoe. Two consecutive measurements were taken from each student and an average of the two measurements was used to calculate the anthropometric indices. The digital balance was calibrated after each measurement. The anthropometric indices were determined based on 2007 WHO growth reference data for children and adolescence (WHO, 2007). Z score value for each student was calculated using Anthro-Plus software based on student sex, age, height, and weight (WHO, 2011). The nutritional status of students was determined based on the information from Z score. The nutritional indicators were labeled as stunting, underweight and wasting based on height-for-age (HAZ), weight-for-age (WAZ) and weight- for -height (WHZ) respectively (WHO,2017). HAZ, WAZ and WHZ score less than – 2 standard deviations (SD) from WHO reference populations were considered as stunted, underweight and waste, respectively. If the Z score value is less than -3 SD, the students were categorized as severely undernourished for each indicator.

Determination of Haemoglobin (HB) Concentration

Haemoglobin concentration was determined according to the method of Cheesbrough (2005). 20 µl (0.02 ml) of venous blood was disposed into 4 ml Drapkin's solution test tube, mixed together with a glass rod. The test tubes were covered using a stopper tube and left at room temperature, protected from light for 5minutes. The mixture of blood sample and the reaent was inserted into the calorimeter machine and the optical density of the Hb measured. Using a prepared table from a calibration graph, the haemoglobin values were read off. .Anaemia was also determined according to age-specific Hb levels using WHO cut-offs. Anaemia was defined as a level of Hb < 11.0 g/dl for children aged 8–11 years, < 11.9 g/dl for children aged 12–14 years and < 12.9 g/dl for children aged ≥ 15 years. Severe anaemia was defined as Hb below 8 g/dl, while moderate anaemia was considered as Hb between 8 and 10.9 g/dl (Shrestha *et al.*, 2018).

Determination of Serum Albumin Level

The serum albumin level was determined using Bromcresol Green (BCG) method as described by Anozie *et al.* (2013).

Determination of Serum Ferritin Level

To determine the Ferritin concentration in serum, a micro plate enzyme immunoassay, colorimetric ELISA Kits (AccuBind ELISA Microwells,USA) was used according to the manufacturers instruction.

RESULTS

Table 1: Prevalence of Intestinal Parasites by Age, Gender and Location

Variables	No. Examined	No. Infected	Prevalence (%)	P-value
Age group (Years)				
5-9	414	127	30.6	
10-12	579	144	24.8	0.246
13-14	207	50	24.1	
Total	1,200	321	26.75	
Gender				
Male	569	149	26.1	
Female	631	172	27.2	0.083
Total	1,200	321	26.75	
Location				
Balanga	200	72	36.0	
Funakaye	200	61	30.5	
Shongom	200	58	29.0	0.001
Akko	200	47	23.5	
Gombe	200	46	23.0	
Kwami	200	37	18.5	
Total	1,200	321	26.75	

Table 2: Percentile Distribution of Infected and Non-Infected Children Based on Height- for- Age-Z-Score (HAZ)

No. Examined	No. Infected (%)	No. Non-Infected (%)	Height -for- Age
8	6(1.8)	2(0.2)	Over Height
1048	240(74.7)	808(91.9)	Normal Height
113	65(20.2)	48(5.4)	Moderately under Height
31	10(3.1)	21(2.3)	Severe under Height
1200	321(26.7)	879(73.2)	Total

$\chi^2=93.02$ p-value=0.063

Table 3: Percentile Distribution of Infected and Non-Infected Children Based on Weight for Age Z-Score (WAZ)

No Examined	Infected (%)	Non-infected (%)	Weight- for- Age
5	4(1.2)	1(0.11)	Over Weight
935	198(61.6)	737(83.8)	Normal Weight
220	91(28.3)	129(14.6)	Moderately under weight
40	28(8.7)	12(1.3)	Severely under weight
1200	321(26.75)	879(73.2)	Total

$\chi^2=80.02$ p-value=0.042

Table 4: Percentile Distribution of Infected and non- Infected Children Based on Weight -for Height- Z-score (WHZ).

No. Examined	Infected (%)	Non-infected (%)	Weight –for- Height
788	252(78.5)	536(60.9)	Well nourished
412	69(21.4)	343(39.0)	Moderate wasting
1200	321(26.7)	879(73.2)	Total

$\chi^2=3.40$ p-value=0.020

Table 5: Prevalence of Anaemia in Infected and Non-Infected Children

Variables	Examined	Anaemic %	Not Anaemic%
Infected	321	67(20.8)	254(79.1)
Gender			
Male	149	29(19.4)	120(80.5)
Female	172	38(22.0)	134(77.9)
Age Group(years)			
5-9	127	31(24.4)	96(75.5)
10-12	144	25(17.3)	119(82.6)
13-14	50	11(22.0)	39(78.0)
Non-Infected	879	21(2.3)	858(97.6)
Gender			
Male	420	8(1.9)	416(99.0)
Female	459	13(2.8)	442(96.2)
Age Group (years)			
5-9	287	10(3.4)	277(96.5)
10-12	435	6(1.3)	429(98.6)
13-14	157	5(3.1)	152(96.8)

$\chi^2=15.460$ p-value=0.001

Table 6: Prevalence of Anaemia in Infected Children with Respect to Type of Parasites

Parasite	Total Infected	Not Anaemic %	Mild %	Moderate %	Anaemic %
<i>S. stercoralis</i>	11	11 (100)	-	-	-
<i>E. vermicularis</i>	12	11 (91.6)	1 (8.3)	-	1 (8.3)
<i>A. lumbricoides</i>	127	101 (79.5)	17 (5.5)	9(15)	26(20.4)
<i>E. histolytica</i>	21	15 (71.4)	6 (28.5)	-	6 (28.5)
<i>E. coli</i>	42	30 (71.4)	5 (11.9)	7 (16.6)	12 (28.5)
<i>T.saginata</i>	20	19 (95.0)	1 (5.0)	-	1 (5.0)
<i>G. lamblia</i>	16	16 (100)	-	-	-
<i>S. mansoni</i>	9	4 (44.4)	3 (33.3)	2 (22.2)	5 (55.5)
<i>H. nana</i>	21	19 (90.4)	2 (10.5)	-	2 (9.5)
Hookworm	23	10 (43.4)	2 (8.6)	11 (47.8)	13 (56.5)
<i>T. trichuira</i>	19	18 (94.7)	-	1 (5.2)	1 (5.2)
Total	321	254 (79.1)	37 (11.5)	30 (9.3)	67 (20.8)

$\chi^2 = 60.882$ df = 48, P.value = 0.100

Key:

Moderate anaemia (7-9.9 g/dl); Mild anaemia (>10-10.9 g/dl); No anemia (>10.9 g/dl)

Table 7: Relationship between Age Group, Gender and Ferritin, Creatinine and Albumin

Variables	Ferritin Mean+SD	Creatinine Mean+SD	Albumin Mean+SD
Age Group(Years)			
5-9	21.51+5.41	55.83+8.75	45.00+2.09
10-12	19.26+5.22	57.83+7.40	44.67+4.50
13-14	18.20+3.89	53.50+8.19	43.55+2.65
Gender			
Male	18.87+4.76	52.84+8.49	44.80+2.40
Female	21.42+5.39	57.27+7.74	44.06+3.31

Table 8: Ferritin, Creatinine and Albumin Deficiency by Age Group and Gender.

Variables Infected (%)	Non Infected (%)	Ferritin Deficient (%)	Creatinine Deficient (%)	Albumin Deficient (%)
Age Group				
5-9	11(28.2)	5(12.8)	16 (41.0)	0
10-12	8(20.5)	3(7.6)	11 (28.2)	0
13-14	8(20.5)	4(10.2)	12(30.7)	0
Total	27 (8.4)	12(1.3)	39 (3.25)	0
Gender				
Male	4(10.2)	9(23.0)	13 (33.3)	0
Female	14(35.8)	12(30.7)	26 (66.6)	0
Total	27(8.4)	12(1.3)	39(3.25)	0

4.1 DISCUSSION

The result of this study reveals an overall prevalence of 26.75% for intestinal parasitic infection which is in agreement with the reports of Gimbe and Dawam (2015) who reported a prevalence of 28%. This study showed a low prevalence of intestinal parasites compare with the prevalences reported by Kabiru (2015) and Destaw (2021) However; it shows a high prevalence compared with the 15.6% reported by Bakari (2023) in Gombe State and 16.6% by Onyenonachiin Imo State (2019). The prevalence rates of individual intestinal parasites vary considerably with altitudes in different parts of the country. These differences could be due to differences in methods used in the study, low-sensitivity of diagnostic method, level of environment sanitation, source of drinking water and educational level of their family as explained by Tamirat, (2018).

With respect to age of the children, it was noted that intestinal parasitic infection was not significantly ($p>0.05$) influenced by age. Younger pupils (5-9) had a higher infection than the other age groups. This could be attributed to younger children being more likely to engage in playing activities, poor hygiene habits, poor toilet training and low immunity against various pathogens leading to low resistance to disease, as explained by Tigabu et al (2010). Kinuthia et al (2012) identified practices such as failure to wash hands and lack of proper toilet training as being major contributor to high prevalence in younger children. The 13-14 years age group was recorded as the age group with the lowest infection. This could

be because of the immunity they developed. Age, nutrition and hormonal level can influence natural or acquired immunity.

In this study, children of both sexes were similarly infected; however female pupils recorded a slightly higher percentage infection than the male.

Dhanbal *et al.*, (2014) pointed out that the infection rate with intestinal parasites is likely to be linked to the everyday activities of people rather than sex. This observation is in agreement with earlier records of Baye (2020), Awolaju and Morcurkeyi (2009) and Allo *et al.*, (2013) who also reported differences in prevalence values of parasites between sexes. However, is in contrast with the findings of Attahiru (2019) and Akua, (2017). The findings many indicate that the differences in gender role are narrowing (Baye, 2020). Epidemiological studies have shown that prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections vary from one locality to other. The prevalence was quite higher in Balanga followed by Funakaye and Shongom. The location with the least prevalence was Kwami. The variations could be due to the level of sanitation and hygiene practices socio economic dwellers and level of education of the parents.

Determination of Relationship between Intestinal Parasitic Infections and Anthropometric Indices among Children Studied

The child is considered as “Malnourished” if he/she is underweight, wasted or stunted. Of the malnourished children, 21.6% were underweight, 12.0% were stunted and 34.3% had wasting. As noted, under nutrition may lead to reduced immunresponses that in turn render the children susceptible to parasitic infection (Tamirat, 2018). Wasting was the most prevalent type of malnutrition recorded in the study areas, followed by under-weight and under height. This was not in line with the findings of Opara *et al.* (2012), who observed under-height as the most prevalent manifestation of malnutrition in school-aged children in Nigeria,

Anthropometric Measurement of Infected and Non Infected Children Based on Height -for -age- Z-Score

Stunting is a long term indicator of chronic malnutrition. The fact that the infected children are moderately and severely under height suggest prolonged nutritional deficiency. Infection might be interfering with nutrient absorption and growth. The finding of this study demonstrated an association between the prevalence of stunting and intestinal parasitic infections among the study children.

Stunting is mostly due long-term poor nutritional intake and is the best indicator of growth retardation in children over long period of time. The prevalence (12.0%) obtained in the present study was below the prevalence recorded by Stephenson *et al.* (2000). Stunting among infected children could suggest chronic nutrient malabsorption due to prolonged parasitic infections. Moreso, *A. lumbricoides* and *Hookworm* are known to reduce nutrient intake leading to growth retardation as documented by Opara *et al.* (2012).

Anthropometric Measurement of Infected and Non Infected Children Based on Weight -for- Age- Z-Score

Weight for age represents both acute and chronic malnutrition. The higher percentage of underweight infected children implies that infections contribute to both long and short term nutritional deficits. The observation of under-weight in non-infected children is a clear indication that it was not associated with intestinal parasitic infection in the study area. It could be because of low socio-economic status of the respondents that may have resulted to protein energy malnutrition.

Anthropometric Measurement of Infected and Non Infected Children Based on Weight -for -Height Z-Score

Wasting is an indicator of acute malnutrition often due to recent food shortages or infections. The high percentage of infected children experiencing moderate wasting suggest that infections may be causing rapid weight loss, possibly due to diarrhea or decreased appetite. Severe wasting was more common in non infected children, which is not associated with intestinal parasitic infections but may be linked to other malnutrition issues.

Prevalence of Anaemia with Respect to Location and Type of Parasite Isolated from Infected Children in the Study Areas

Anaemia was higher ($P>0.05$) in infected children than non-infected children. This was in agreement with the study conducted by Orji (2015). The prevalence of anaemia in infected children was lower when compared with the prevalence reported by Ehiaghe *et al.* (2013) and also by Leal *et al.* (2011).

Anemia in infected children varied significantly with respect to location ($P<0.05$). The highest prevalence of moderate anaemia recorded in Gombe could be attributed to socioeconomic factors such as poverty and household size. The association between low haemoglobin and parasite positivity seems possible because intestinal parasites are lodged in the duodenum and jejunum, the site of iron absorption. Hookworm infection could predispose an infected child to anaemia due to feeding activities of hookworm. This study confirmed association between intestinal parasitic infections and the risk of anemia in the subjects as well. Children infected with intestinal parasites were more anemic than those who were not infected.

Relationship between Age Group, Gender and Ferritin, Creatinine and Albumin

Ferritin is a key biomarker for iron storage in the body. The findings indicated a higher ferritin level among females compared to males. This aligns with studies such as Mwangi *et al.* (2021), which found that prepubescent and adolescent females are more prone to iron deficiency due to menstrual losses and lower dietary iron intake. Similarly, Brittenham *et al.* (2018) highlighted that iron-deficiency anemia is more common in school-age girls due to hormonal influences and differences in dietary habits. Age-related trends in ferritin levels revealed a decline in ferritin as children grow older, suggesting increased iron demands during growth spurts. Studies by Jelliffe and Jelliffe (2017) support this, emphasizing that rapid growth phases in children, particularly during adolescence, require higher iron intake to meet physiological demands.

Creatinine, a byproduct of muscle metabolism, serves as an indicator of renal function and muscle mass. The study revealed that males had significantly higher creatinine levels than females, a trend widely reported in research (Janssen *et al.*, 2000). This difference can be attributed to higher muscle mass in males, as supported by Bakris *et al.* (2019), who observed that sex-related differences in muscle mass influence baseline creatinine levels. With respect to age, creatinine levels increased with age, reflecting progressive muscle development. A study by Dossa *et al.* (2017) demonstrated a strong correlation between muscle mass, age, and creatinine levels, emphasizing the importance of protein intake and physical activity in maintaining optimal creatinine levels in children.

Albumin, a key protein involved in maintaining oncotic pressure and transport of essential nutrients, showed deficiency patterns influenced by gender and age. The study found that males had higher albumin levels than females, consistent with findings by Adegbite *et al.* (2018), who reported albumin levels is more significantly higher in females due to hormonal and metabolic differences. Age-related trends showed a decline in albumin levels among older children, similar to findings by Moyo *et al.* (2015).

Ferritin, Creatinine and Albumin Deficiency in Relation to Gender and Age of Children

The analysis examined the relationship between ferritin, albumin and creatinine levels and intestinal parasitic infections. The result showed a statistical significant relationship ($p<0.005$) between intestinal parasite infections and ferritin deficiency. This aligns with the work of Favour *et al.* (2011). He stated that infections with parasites particularly Hookworm, *A. lumbricoides* can cause iron deficiency. This could be as a result of parasite burden, which causes chronic blood loss, malabsorption and inflammation-induced sequestration.

Albumin levels did not show an association with intestinal parasitic infections ($p>0.005$) as zero deficiency was recorded. Moyo *et al.* (2015) noted that protein-losing enteropathy is more common in severe parasitic infections. Since the study recorded moderate infection and malnutrition, the impact on albumin may not be as pronounced. The zero deficiency of albumin recorded could be because not all parasites cause severe protein loss. *G lamblia* is more likely to affect fat absorption than protein status as explained by Mahmud *et al.* (2020). He also stated that the liver can increase albumin synthesis unless there is prolonged protein deficiency.

No significant relationship between creatinine level and parasitic infections. This finding aligns with the work of Dosa *et al.* (2017) who found out that creatinine level remained normal in children with mild

malnutrition and infection, but decrease in cases of severe protein-energy malnutrition. Njenga *et al.* (2019) noted that chronic kidney disease in children is rarely caused by parasites, except in cases of heavy infection with *schistosoma spp* or severe malaria. The zero deficiency of creatinine recorded in this study could be because creatinine is a byproduct of muscle metabolism, unless in the case of severe malnutrition or muscle wasting is present, creatinine level remain stable. Also, dehydration can elevate creatinine level, masking any deficiency. Most intestinal infections do not directly impair kidney function. The influence of gender on albumin, ferritin and creatinine deficiencies show variations in ferritin levels, while albumin and creatinine deficiencies show no significant difference as zero deficiency was recorded. Albumin level did not show any significant difference. This suggests that both male and female children had similar protein nutritional status. This is in agreement with the report of Adegbite (2018). He found no significant gender difference in albumin level among children. Similarly, Moyo (2015) observed that gender did not influence albumin level in children thus, albumin levels appear less influenced gender suggesting that diet and disease severity may play bigger role than gender-based differences. It was recorded by WHO (2020) that albumin is not easily depleted; the body has mechanisms to maintain albumin homeostasis, even in mild to moderate malnutrition. They further explained that unless severe protein energy malnutrition (PEM) or chronic infections are present, albumin levels remain relatively stable across genders. Similar to albumin, the result showed no significant differences in creatinine levels. This agrees with the study conducted by Dossa *et al.* (2017). He reported creatinine levels did not differ significantly by gender. The findings of this study suggest that creatinine levels are primarily influenced by over all nutritional status rather than gender difference.

The analysis revealed that female children had significantly higher ferritin deficiency compared to females. This finding is not consistent with previous research by Nacher (2004), showing that iron deficiency is often more prevalent in young boys than girls. He further explained that males have a weaker immune response to infections, making them more susceptible to parasitic-induced inflammation and anaemia.

Iron deficiency was more common in 5-9 age groups. This implies that younger children are at greater risk for iron deficiency, possibly due to higher growth demands, immune differences and dietary factors.

4.2 CONCLUSION

The overall prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections was 26.75%. This study showed that there was moderately low prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections in Gombe State. Malnutrition recorded in the study might be due to intestinal parasitic infections. This study showed that malnutrition occurs regardless of sex and age among school-aged children. Intestinal parasitic infections were associated with anemia in the study areas. Serum ferritin levels were also significantly reduced among infected children, indicating iron deficiency and protein-energy malnutrition linked to chronic parasitic burden.

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